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THE FUTURE EDUCATION DELIVERY MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The online education system has got a major boost in recent years. Social distancing as a norm has created a big opportunity for the online education system. Content-wise the educational material may not change. But there is a drastic change in the “supply chain” and “logistics” of the delivery system of education. Hitherto students were going to the teachers to get educated. A 360-degree change has stepped into this basic model. The future education delivery model is one where the teachers will be reaching the students to deliver education. The new model has several advantages as well as limitations. This article takes stock of the future education delivery model in the form of an online education system. 100 students and 100 teachers were interviewed by way of a close-ended questionnaire to assess the feasibility of the model in terms of opportunities and challenges of the online model. The results are discussed in detail in the article. A wide agreement was found on the opportunities and challenges for online education as a future education delivery model. However, challenges were found to be overweighing the opportunities.

KEYWORDS: Online education, Challenges, Opportunities, Infrastructure..

1. INTRODUCTION

The online education system has been in vogue for more than a decade now. It made inroads in a country like India through companies like Byjus. This article takes stock of the future education delivery model in the form of an online education system. Before discussing the development of the online education system in India, the global developments are discussed briefly as under:

1.1 Global developments in online education

Online education or web-based learning alludes to the strategy for content scattering and quick learning through the use of data innovation and Internet innovation. The "e" of e-Learning represents electronic learning, effective learning, exploratory learning, experiential learning, extended learning, expanded learning, simple to-utilize learning, and improved learning. The United States is the origination of e-learning. After 1998, e-Learning has been being spread around the world and has quickly extended from North America and Europe to Asia. Online education is one of the significant educational techniques today. It has grown quickly around the globe and has bit by bit become a significant class of school education. Nations around the globe are effectively investigating how to viably teach students through the Internet, and numerous genuine

instances of online education have developed, bringing about numerous valuable experiences in online education. Albeit online education is growing quickly around the globe, more uses of online education are utilized as an enhancement to ordinary school education. In the standardized education and teaching practice, more students go to schools to partake in customary homeroom teaching, and enormous scope online education needs down to earth application situations. The flare-up of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China, toward the end of 2019, was a significant public health crisis that had the quickest spread, the most extensive extent of disease, and the hardest to forestall and control in China since its foundation (Xinhuanet, 2020). Influenced by the epidemic, the administration requires divisions at all levels to compose powers to restrain or stop production and requires non-essential ventures to suspend production and business operations, and typical financial and social exercises were significantly influenced (Guangming.com, 2020). The World Health Organization-China Joint Expert Expedition calls the ground-breaking public health measures China has taken in light of the COVID-19 epidemic, which might be "the most aspiring, adaptable and dynamic malady control in mankind's history" (People's Network, 2020). While obstructing the spread of the COVID-19 epidemic to schools, to decrease the impact of the epidemic on education, since February 4, 2020, the Leading Group of the Ministry of Education of China to respond to the COVID-19 epidemic has given the "About Guiding Opinions on Online Teaching Organization and Management of General Colleges and Universities during the Period, Notice on Supporting Education and Teaching with Information Technology during Epidemic Prevention and Control, and Several Suggestions on Targeted Teacher Work during Epidemic Prevention and Control Notice".

1.2 Developments in India in online education

Online education in India has made considerable progress with the advancement of innovation. India is one of the countries that are creating at an exponential rate as far as innovation. With a population of more than 1.3 billion, the accessibility of rapid web and cell phones, India has the most number of innovatively determined people. The ascent of the web has changed the lifestyle in India. Individuals like to do everything online, they shop online, work together online, make companions online, learn online and so on, while, eCommerce is the most noteworthy online industry, online education and learning stand directly close to it. With the ever-expanding data accessible on the web and the innumerable number of online courses, numerous individuals in India want to learn online.

By seeing the potential and enormous ubiquity of advanced innovation in India, Our Honourable Prime Minister has imagined changing our country and making open doors for all residents by saddling computerized advances through Digital India activity. The activity involves different undertakings in different territories identifying with health, education, labour, business, and so on. As a piece of Digital India venture, numerous schools and colleges offer online correspondence courses. Presently we should experience a portion of the intriguing realities about online education with regards to India.

1.3 Key facts about online education with regard to India

- The online education market in India was worth \$ 247 million out of 2016, which is expected to develop about \$ 1.96 billion by 2021. That is a compound yearly development rate of 52%.
- The number of users enrolled for different online learning courses is evaluated to be 1.6 million in 2016, which is expected to develop about 9.6 million before the end of 2021.
- It is assessed that there is a 175% expansion in the cost of classroom education, this gives online education progressively favoured because it is cost compelling.
- Almost 48% population in India between 15–40 age groups with high aspirations, however lower pay is a decent objective market for online education. Furthermore, the adequacy of online direct is high in the younger demographic.

These components show the contribution and future potential of online education in India. In the backdrop of Covid-19, a big window of opportunity has been opened for online education.

1.4 Objectives of the study

This article has been written with the following objectives:

1. To take stock of recent developments in online education
2. To assess the opportunities for online education in India
3. To assess the challenges for online education in India
4. To find out of the challenges outweigh the opportunities for online education in India

Following research questions were probed:

1. RQ1 – What are the recent developments in online education?
2. RQ2 – What are the opportunities for online education in India?
3. RQ3 - What are the challenges for online education in India?
4. RQ4 – Does the challenges outweigh the opportunities for online education in India

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The satisfying worldwide need for developing the science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) workforce requires solutions for the deficiency of qualified educators. We propose and assess a model for scaling up moderate access to successful STEM education through national online education stages. These stages permit asset compelled advanced education foundations to receive online courses created by the nation's top universities and divisions. A multisite randomized controlled preliminary tried this model with completely online and mixed instruction modalities in Russia's online education stage. We locate that online and mixed instruction produce comparable understudy learning results as traditional in-person instruction at considerably lower costs. Embracing this model at scale diminishes faculty pay costs that can support increments in STEM enrollment (Chirikov *et al.*, 2020).

Education is a spine of any nation which is mercilessly crushed during this pandemic. The entire educational framework has been abruptly moved carefully which is a colossal test for both the students and educators to adapt operation too. Since the education framework has been flipped around, is it a test, help, or revile for creating nations like India? In this article, we will consider the difficulties of online education and it was discovered that it has both positive and negative impacts on Education and in this way, we can say that advanced education framework ought to be equipped and need to fortify the web availability Pan India (Goswami, 2020).

The world community is resolved to accomplish 17 objectives prominently known as United Nation Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs) of which education has been given a significant push that has been reserved in Goal 4. As a part nation, India likewise endeavoured to address the issues of education with the most noteworthy priority that is envisaged by the reactions of the legislature for drafting the New Education Policy in 2019. The administration is resolved to accomplish comprehensive education that needs the manifestation of the e-Learning stage. Since it is hard to bring the immense population under the ambit of the ordinary education framework, this paper has endeavoured to investigate the encounters and difficulties of e-Learning mechanism in the advanced education arrangement of India (Taso and Chakravarty, 2020).

New age technology platforms help in surveying the exhibition of students, educators, and organizations in general and are progressively being embraced by educational establishments in India. Cloud-based platforms that assist the classroom with going paperless are additionally discovering takers. Likewise separated from the most recent improvements in ICT classrooms, Augmented Reality and Virtual reality are being received in the field of education. The study was expected to examine issues identified with e-Learning in advanced education in India alongside the investigation of the prospect of e-Learning in the related zone. The exploration has been done with the Under Graduate students and resources of Mumbai and its rural areas. The study shows the beneficial outcomes of e-Learning for the advanced education framework in India. What's more, the best way to support a superior future is by instructing the younger age with successful and effective education philosophies (Mehta *et al.*, 2020).

Online education has begun picking up fame in India over the most recent couple of years. The Government of India's endeavours to enable youth by offering them quality education liberated from cost or at the costs they can stand to pay has offered to ascend to Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) (Saxena, 2020).

At present, India doesn't have a major market for e-learning, yet there is tremendous potential in the nation. The current study might be useful for the educational foundations in India and incomparable creating nations in understanding the students' points of view on e-learning selection. The educational organizations may improve their frameworks as needs are with the goal that they cannot just hold the students of their nations, yet besides draw in students from different nations for additional education. E-learning can be utilized to give clients snappy access to thoughts and encounters from a wide range of individuals, networks, and the cultures to expand the substantial-quality (Phutela and Dwivedi, 2020).

The improvement of the online learning situations inside those foundations with the goal that learning would not upset. The crown virus pandemic has tried the status of focuses to manage an emergency that requires online and remote measures. Presently, a day the web, learning is available to all. Henceforth, individuals in the nations where traditional learning is confronting different obstructions can exploit online courses. Up until now, e-learning has been powerful to the individuals that comprehended its worth. It offers the opportunity to have incredible outcomes for lower costs and now and again for no costs by any means. Regardless of this, online learning has numerous points of interest. Education may have a few purposes and online courses help to satisfy it. E-learning can upset education as it gives new chances to traditional getting the hang of (Singh, 2020).

A comprehensive study focusing on opportunities and challenges for the online education system in India has not been seen of late.

3. METHODS

3.1 Data collection

The following methodology was designed for the study to collect primary data.

- a. Select using random sampling 100 school and college teachers
- b. Select using random sampling 100 school and college students
- c. Design and validate a 10-point each questionnaire for opportunities and challenges
- d. Seek responses on a 5-point agree-disagree scale
- e. Conduct the survey
- f. Summarize the responses
- g. Apply a t-test at 95% confidence level
- h. Analyse the results

3.2 Hypotheses

The hypotheses set in this regard were as under:

- H_{01} – There are no significant opportunities for online education in India
- H_{a1} - There are significant opportunities for online education in India
- H_{02} - There are no significant challenges for online education in India
- H_{a2} - There are significant challenges for online education in India
- H_{03} – The challenges do not outweigh the opportunities
- H_{a3} – The challenges outweigh the opportunities

The study was conducted in Mumbai. The 10 opportunities identified based on the literature review were as under:

Sr. No.	Opportunities
1	A substantial population of school-going children
2	Technology-pro Government
3	Reduction in the cost of delivering education

4	Social distancing possible
5	Large reach
6	Convenient learning
7	Interactive learning
8	Implementation of an assignment system of learning
9	Improved access to faculty
10	Global exposure

The 10 challenges identified based on the literature review were as under:

Sr. No.	Challenges
1	Misuse of internet
2	Penetration at the rural level
3	Incompetent faculty
4	Problems with internet
5	Cultural issues
6	Hardware infrastructure
7	Software support
8	Language barriers
9	Problem with smaller kids
10	Likely physical and mental problems

3.3 Scheme formed for the testing of hypotheses

- a. Responses would be collected under 2 sections (opportunities and challenges) of the questionnaire on a 5-point agree-disagree scale,
- b. The responses under each of the sections would be aggregated under two groups of agree and disagree,
- c. While doing so for each of the extreme responses, a weight of 2 would be to distinguish them from the non-extreme responses,
- d. For each of the question, an average count will be calculated in the two opposites,
- e. Percentages to questions under a particular section of the questionnaire will be averaged to get a single score for that section,
- f. The section-wise average score percentage will be compared with a hypothesized mean of the population of 50% score connoting an event by chance and not due to statistical significance,
- g. P-values will be calculated and the null hypotheses will be checked for rejection or non-rejection. These calculations would be done at a 95% confidence level using a t-test since the standard deviation (SD) of the population is not known.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive analysis of the sample (Table set 5)

4.1.1 Area of respondents

Sr. No.	Area	Number of respondents-teachers	Percentage	Number of respondents-students	Percentage
1	Dadar	14	14%	9	9%
2	Chembur	10	10%	12	12%
3	Worli	14	14%	15	15%
4	Mahim	12	12%	8	8%
5	Kurla	7	7%	5	5%
6	Andheri	11	11%	13	13%
7	Goregaon	11	11%	6	6%
8	Boriwali	8	8%	9	9%
9	Bandra	6	6%	12	12%
10	Dahisar	7	7%	11	11%
	Total	100	100%	100	100%

4.1.2 Gender

Sr. No.	Gender	Number of respondents-teachers	Percentage	Number of respondents-students	Percentage
1	Male	52	52%	49	49%
2	Female	48	48%	51	51%
	Total	100	100%	100	100%

4.1.3 Age

Sr. No.	Age-group	Number of respondents-teachers	Percentage	Age-group	Number of respondents-students	Percentage
1	20-29 years	10	10%	<12 years	24	24%
2	30-39 years	58	58%	12-15 years	25	25%
3	40-49 years	23	23%	15-20 years	41	41%
4	>=50 years	9	9%	>=20 years	10	10%
	Total	100	100%	Total	100	100%

4.1.4 Category of a teaching institution

Sr. No.	Category	Number of respondents-teachers	Percentage	Number of respondents-students	Percentage
1	Government	25	25%	28	28%
2	Private	51	51%	42	42%
3	Trust	24	24%	30	30%
	Total	100	100%	100	100%

4.1.5 Experience in teaching-learning

Sr. No.	Experience	Number of respondents-teachers	Percentage	Number of respondents-students	Percentage
1	< 5 years	20	20%	72	72%
2	5-10 years	31	31%	28	28%
3	>10 years	49	49%	0	0%
	Total	100	100%	100	100%

4.2 Inferential analysis**4.2.1 Agreement percentages to opportunities**

Sr. No.	Opportunities	Teachers	Students
1	A substantial population of school-going children	75%	69%
2	Technology-pro Government	76%	72%
3	Reduction in the cost of delivering education	78%	84%
4	Social distancing possible	69%	81%
5	Large reach	75%	78%
6	Convenient learning	72%	76%
7	Interactive learning	74%	79%
8	Implementation of an assignment system of learning	77%	69%
9	Improved access to faculty	79%	72%
10	Global exposure	68%	71%
Average		74%	75%
SD (Standard Deviation)		0.03653	0.05259
H1 (Hypothesized Mean)		50%	50%
Ho (Sample Mean)		0.74	0.75
n (Sample size)		100	100
t-value		66.52	47.73
p-value		0.0000	0.0000

Since the p-values are <0.0001 the null hypothesis that there are no significant opportunities for online education in India stands rejected.

4.2.2 Agreement percentages to challenges

Sr. No.	Challenges	Teachers	Students
1	Misuse of internet	80%	91%
2	Penetration at the rural level	81%	90%
3	Incompetent faculty	79%	92%
4	Problems with internet	84%	93%
5	Cultural issues	86%	86%
6	Hardware infrastructure	88%	89%
7	Software support	89%	90%
8	Language barriers	90%	88%
9	Problem with smaller kids	93%	89%
10	Likely physical and mental problems	91%	90%
Average		86%	90%
SD (Standard Deviation)		0.04909	0.01989
H1 (Hypothesized Mean)		50%	50%
Ho (Sample Mean)		0.86	0.90
n (Sample size)		100	100
t-value		73.54	200.11
p-value		0.0000	0.0000

Since the p-values are <0.0001 the null hypothesis that there are no significant challenges for online education in India stands rejected.

For testing the 3rd hypothesis, average agreement percentages for the two groups of teachers and students were compared and results were as under:

Variable	Observations	Obs. with missing data	Obs. without missing data	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
Opportunity	10	0	10	0.695	0.810	0.747	0.031
Challenge	10	0	10	0.855	0.910	0.880	0.022

t-test for two independent samples / two-tailed test: 95% confidence interval on the difference between the means: [-0.157,-0.108]

Difference	-0.133
t (Observed value)	-11.162
t (Critical value)	2.101
DF	18
p-value (Two-tailed)	< 0.0001
alpha	0.05

Test interpretation

- H_0 : The difference between the means is equal to 0.
- H_a : The difference between the means is different from 0.

As the computed p-value is lower than the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, one should reject the null hypothesis H_0 , and accept the alternative hypothesis H_a . The null hypothesis that the challenges do not outweigh the opportunities stands rejected.

4.3 Discussion

The average agreement for the opportunities as per teachers is 74%, while as per the students it is 75%. The average agreement for the challenges as per teachers is 86%, while as per the students it is 90%. The average agreement for the opportunities as per teachers and students is 75%, while the average agreement for the challenges as per teachers and students is 88%. In the case of both opportunities and challenges, the agreement level is substantially higher than 50% to accept them as significant. At the same time, the difference between the agreement levels to challenges is much higher than that of the opportunities. Hence the challenges for online education outweigh the opportunities.

5. CONCLUSION

There is a wide agreement on the various opportunities for online education in India. Sizable agreement percentages were recorded for opportunities like Substantial population of school-going children, Technology-pro Government, Reduction in cost of delivering education, Social distancing possible, Large reach, Convenient learning, Interactive learning, Implementation of assignment system of learning, Improved access to faculty and Global exposure from both teachers and students. Similarly, there was a sizable agreement for the challenges on the part of both teachers and students. Challenges like Misuse of the internet, Penetration at the rural level, Incompetent faculty, Problems with the internet, Cultural issues, Hardware infrastructure, Software support, Language barriers, Problem with smaller kids, and Likely physical and mental problems were widely accepted. On an overall basis, it is concluded that the challenges outweigh the opportunities. All the stakeholders will have to take concrete steps to address the challenges so that online education can become a successful new model of delivering education in India. The government should spend more on improving the technological infrastructure. Training of the teachers is also important. Delivery education online demands special skills and teachers will have to work on those to gain proficiency.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Chirikov, I.; Semenova, T.; Maloshonok, N.; Bettinger, E. and Kizilcec, R. F. (2020), "Online education platforms scale college STEM instruction with equivalent learning outcomes at lower cost", *Science Advances*, Vol. 6, Issue 15, pp. 5324.

- Goswami, S. (2020), Online Education in Corona Outbreak: A Challenge, Boon or Curse in India, *Boon or Curse in India (May 28, 2020)*.
- Guangming.com (2020), Economic impact of new coronary pneumonia and policy suggestions, available at: https://theory.gmw.cn/2020-02/10/content_33541497.htm,02-10/2020-03-11.
- Kumar, Atul (2019), “A Study of Significant Characteristics of E-payment Regime in India”, *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 7, Special Issue 1, May, pp. 168-174.
- Mehta, S.; Tiwari, P.; Maniyar, F. and Rahman, T. (2020), “Emerging Trends of E-Learning in Indian Higher Education: Challenges and Opportunities”, *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology*, Vol. XII, Issue III, pp. 14-20.
- People’s Network (2020) “China demonstrates the image of a responsible great country with practical actions” (see the truth and the common situation to combat the epidemic situation), available at: <http://world.people.com.cn/n1/2020/0226/c1002-31604381.html,02-26/2020-03-11>.
- Phutela, N. and Dwivedi, S. (2020), “A qualitative study of students' perspective on e-learning adoption in India”, *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-02-2019-0041>.
- Saxena, K. (2020), Coronavirus Accelerates Pace of Digital Education in India, EDII educational repository.
- Shimpi, Jayant and Manjare, Sagar O. (2019), “Social Media Marketing - Student Admission in Higher Education”, *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 7, Issue 2, pp. 174-179.
- Singh, S. (2020), Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Education System, *Tathapi*, Vol. 19, Issue 26, pp. 58-63.
- Taso, K. and Chakrabarty, A. (2020), “E-learning in Higher Education in India: Experiences and Challenges - An Exploratory Study’, *Intelligent Computing and Innovation on Data Science*, pp. 715-723.
- Xinhuanet (2019), The Ministry of Education of the People’s Republic of China interprets “China Education Modernization 2035” and its implementation plan (2018-2022).

ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

Creativity and innovations are indispensable for the growth of business and the success of the organization. It is an important factor which helps traditional companies and educational institutions in foreseeing the potential threats and rising competition. Needless to say, companies and organizations cannot thrive without matching the pace with the change and transformation which is taking place in the market. Digital transformation integrates digital technologies into all areas of a business. To meet with the ever changing demands of business processes and customer expectations and create a competitive advantage as well as positioning the organization for the future growth, the role of digital transformation and innovation cannot be ignored. IoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Automation, Machine Learning, Block Chain are some of the latest technologies which have brought about the sea of change by amalgamating demanding millennial generation into the high speed data lanes. In the past few months of Lockdown, digitalization has played a vital role in sustaining the global economic condition. Businesses are now looking for the new ways of dealings and cost minimization. Educational institutions also embraced digital mode of teaching and learning methodologies in order to minimize the impact of pandemic on the academics of students. This conference is intended to seek intellectual contribution of experts from industry, academia and research for embracing change & transformation through innovations and creativity.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Time of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian Management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

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